

Workplace Spirituality Paradigm at Public and Private Schools of Punjab, Pakistan

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Abstract

The main focus of this paper was to compare the workplace spirituality paradigm at public and private schools. The study was quantitative, descriptive in nature and survey method was approached to collect data. The researchers developed rating scale comprising of seventeen dimensions of workplace spirituality paradigm which was upgraded and validated in the response of expert educational opinion and piloted before actual data collection. The sample of the study was 270 participants of public and private schools of the division Sahiwal. The dimensions of workplace spirituality like teachers satisfied with their job, work connectedness with life requirement, teachers think about values and worth of the institution, linking of work and social goodness of community, promotion of creativeness of spirit of community, work spirituality reduces job pressure, teachers work in the institution as a family, and the teachers feel sense of joy are best experienced in public schools as compared to private schools. The dimensions of workplace spirituality like meaningfulness in work, teachers promote climate of mutual trust and respect, discipline is maintained, priority of caring is important, sense of humanity at workplace, increase energy value and spirit of the teachers at the workplace, connectedness with goals and objectives of the institution and the teachers goes to institution happily experienced better in private schools as compared to public schools.

Keywords: Workplace Spirituality, Public schools, Dimensions, Meaningful work, Sense of humanity, Compared.

Introduction

According to Sandhu (2015), workplace spirituality is the ability of acceptance of employee inner life nourishment by purposeful work occurs for the benefit of a community. Work spirituality is related to the employees' behaviour, response, experience, and soul towards gratitude of linking to one another with meaningful activities and a sense of purpose at their workplace. The teachers' community is the spiritual persons who have personal intellect competencies, values, and worth in their lives and in their professional attitudes. The term workplace spirituality gives a sense of pleasure among individuals to remain united in their work with patience, giving direction, relationship, and connectedness at work.

The term workplace spirituality is defined as "it is a framework of organizational values evidenced in the culture that promotes employees' experience of transcendence through the work process, facilitating their sense of being connected to others in a way that provided feelings of completeness and joy" (Giacalone & Jurkiewicz, 2003). Schutte (2016) pointed out that workplace spirituality is a definite postmodern trend, tool and a process taken seriously in business and leadership development.

Workplace spirituality is the totality of meaningful work, the pleasure of society and experience value of the institution. Workplace spirituality dimensions had a significant impact on work satisfaction with mediating trust positively. The enhanced communication patterns are produced in the teachers with the assistance of the promotion of workplace spirituality criteria (Hassan, Nadeem & Akhter, 2016).

The different dimensions and measures of spirituality like meaningful work, general conscious awareness of community and linking of employee ethical values with institutional value are studied by Ahmad and Omar (2016). The employees' survey response shows that employees have a higher degree of spirituality and meaningfulness in work as compared to other dimensions like the sensation of community and values orientation. The responsibility of the organization was to provide a favorable working place which enhances the

spirituality in the employees at the workplace. The researcher also suggested to, compare the experience of individuals in workplace spirituality in the public and private sector.

Wainaina, Iravo & Waititu (2014) described that workplace spirituality is an internal abstract part and act as a causal element of organizational commitment. Employees are regarded as the most important pillars of any organization. The main focus of this study was to “establish the effect of workplace spirituality on organizational commitment of academic staff” The statistical analysis like correlation and regression portrayed that significant positive relations are found in the workplace spirituality and institutional commitment.

Bell, Rajendran & Theiler (2012) investigated the effect of workplace spirituality on different human resource management prospects. The workplace spirituality effects on well being, ill-being and job pressure or threat and stress. These parameters of spirituality positively or negatively effect on organizational performance. The correlation analysis shows that these parameters or variables correlated moderately with each other.

The key performance parameters such as organizational commitment, job performance and spirituality at a workplace are interrelated with each other. Organizational commitment consisted of three factors like (1) affective commitment, (2) continuance commitment and (3) normative commitment whereas the connectedness between the institution and individual needs, the natural ability of enjoyment, beneficence to public and happening of inner life are the factors of workplace spirituality. The workplace spirituality put a positive effect on affective and normative commitments. The variables; gender, stream, age, and rank have also effect on job performance (Campbell & Hwa, 2014).

Fernando & Nilakant (2008) established a self-actualizing workplace spirituality model. The self-actualizing spirituality model consists of three parts; need activity and goal. The need component relates to innate need and self which prompts to lead to the next component. The activity section relating to cognitive, self reflection and behavioural approach which includes practices values and accommodation procedure. The last portion of the model includes experiencing the ultimate, self unification and experiencing the oughtness. The individual spirituality at their workplace leads to accomplishing their needs to grow and rise towards the ideal, ought and best.

Kumpikaite & Valiuniene (2014) concluded that some differences are found about spirituality at work in Euro-partners and Lithuanian group. The idea of Euro-partners was that the spirituality related values not only corresponds to the individual but also involve to organizational life whereas this discourse more strengthens than Lithuanian group.

The objective of the study

The major objective of this research study was to compare the workplace spirituality paradigm at public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan.

Research question

The research question of the study was to compare the workplace spirituality paradigm at public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan.

Methods and Procedure of the Study

The present study was quantitative in nature, and survey approach was used to collect data. All the secondary school's teachers were the target population. The province of Punjab was administratively divided into nine divisions, and the researchers were interested in conducting research in Sahiwal division. The division Sahiwal has three districts, i.e., Pakpattan, Sahiwal and Okara. The researchers selected fifteen (15) secondary level public and private schools from each district of Sahiwal division. Three (3) teachers from each public and private school were selected on a random basis from ninety (90) schools. Thus the sample was comprised of 270 teachers from the public and private schools. The rating scale consists of seventeen statements related to workplace spirituality were developed as a tool of the study. The instrument rating scale was piloted in that school which was not included in the sample and validity was also checked from the educational experts before data survey.

Review of the Related Literature

Emery (2016) explained the relationship between leadership, decision making and spirituality by the use of fry theory of spiritual leadership. This study presented that there is no significant factor was found between leadership, decision making, and workplace spirituality. The organization develops strategic plans that involve spirituality to promote the decision making process of individuals at the workplace. The utilization of better decision made on the basis of workplace spirituality helped the leaders and organization to access the influence of spirituality element at the workplace and also improve the quality and effectiveness of the decision making process.

Jena & Pradhan (2014) portrayed that significant relationship was found in spiritual competencies and work life balance moderately irrespective of demographic factors whereas suggested as revitalizing both components for promoting an effective behavior in the organizational settings.

The function of spirituality at workplace played moderately relationship between soft TQM and organizational commitment. This philosophy experienced to foster positive attitudes of employees in the organization — the title workplace spirituality associated at individual, groups and organizational level. The research portrayed that soft TQM dimensions influence employees work behaviors. The management process may select to an emphasis on different parameters of soft TQM which depends on the performance (Adawiyah, Shariff, Saud & Mokhtar, 2011).

Ferreira (2013) through a phenomenological approach presented 34 core items of workplace spirituality. Workplace spirituality includes the experiences to explore the real purpose of life, to establish a positive association with colleagues and have stable consistency in core, beliefs, and values of the organization. The spirituality at work leads to organizational performance by three elements like human resources, philosophical and interpersonal perspective (Beheshtifar & Zare, 2013).

A significant positive relationship was found between workplace spirituality and self esteem with psychological well-being. The self esteem and workplace spirituality are the estimation of psychological well being (Awan & Sitwat, 2014). Wahid & Noriza (2014) presented a study to point out “the influence of workplace spirituality on knowledge sharing activities, emphasizing on the communities of practice which described as an important knowledge contributor through their willingness to share their implicit knowledge with their fellow colleagues, deliberating the perspective of workplace spirituality” If the employees experienced spirituality at workplace, more affectively associated with the institution, observe a sense of obligation and loyalty with respect to organization which increases job commitment and ultimately enhance individual and organizational performance.

Biswakarma (2018) indicated a positive relationship between workplace spirituality and productivity whereas workplace spirituality positively influences employee productivity. Workplace spirituality played a key role to make the employee productive and satisfied. The employees became more advantageous over the long run as compared with employees working in the institutions where spirituality is neglected. It should be needed to make their organization spiritual and provide a spiritual environment which emphasize spiritual leadership.

Marschke, Preziosi, & Harrington (2009) described that in coming century to face the worsening of business and worldwide competition, so it is necessitated for business leaders and employees to stroke into their spiritual assets. Giacalone & Jurkiewicz (2003) examined individual ethical or unethical spirituality influences business practice. When there is spirituality in the workplace, the organization enjoys a great market value and is more able to attract investment. The employees in low spiritual organizations think as servants while employees express their creativity and unpack innovative ways in spiritual organizations. Spiritual organizations provide resources to employees to do their jobs well and give value, respect the culture, religion, and language (Nicolaidis, 2016).

The inclusion of spirituality in the workplace achieved a large number of individual and organizational goals like purposefulness in work, beliefs, and fertility. The parameters of spirituality are ethics, social rites and sense of public which are established in the workplace. The development of these parameters propagates workplace

spirituality and enhances the personal and organizational business prosperity (Mark & Gerald, 2005). Chia (2012) indicated a negative association between workplace spirituality and earnings management, means workplace spirituality decreases the conditions for earnings management. Ke, Zhang, Yan & Fu (2017) presented a model which indicated that the workplace spirituality of teaching staff had a direct bearing on job commitment while professional commitment considers the mediating role. The institution should develop spirituality paradigm. Spirituality is found positively significant in anticipating the affective commitment among the staff (Usman & Danish, 2010).

Liang, Peng, Zhao & Wu, (2017) found that our sense of living a meaningful life influences on our sense of psychological well-being. The higher will of freedom, will to meaning, positive sense of the meaning of our life, the higher will of psychological well-being. This study is designed for teaching professionals. When a teacher experiences hurdles in teaching, classroom management and parent teacher relations in the workplace, worked with spirituality. The values of spiritual persons develop and bestowed to the ornamentation of persons which leads to the accretion of virtue and are considered to be ethical persons significantly advantages to their organizations (McGhee & Grant, 2008). Workplace spirituality is compatible with life satisfaction and the mediating role of attitude (Bakhtiari, Fathi, Ahagh, Hosseininejad & Ahmadboukan, 2018). An organizational leader put incentive the employees with the servant leadership style. This approach gives aids to the workforce to make the workplace to be more beneficial for society (Khan, Khan & Chaudhry, 2015).

Presentation and Analysis of Results

Table 1: Comparison of Workplace Spirituality at Public and Private Sectors

Sr. No	Dimensions of Workplace Spirituality	Mean		Standard Dev.		t	Sig.
		Public	Private	Public	Private		
1	Meaningfulness in work	3.485	3.696	1.1719	1.1586	-2.356	.019
2	Teachers satisfied with their job	3.541	3.393	1.2291	1.0614	-1.658	.099
3	Work connectedness with life requirement	3.563	3.263	1.0914	1.0946	3.711	.000
4	Teachers think about values and worth of the institution	3.844	3.444	1.0083	1.0677	4.968	.000
5	Teachers promotes climate of mutual trust and respect	3.419	3.641	1.0591	.9209	-2.661	.008
6	Disciplined is maintained	3.119	3.519	1.1857	.9933	-4.504	.000
7	Priority of caring is important	3.459	3.615	1.0185	.9124	-1.883	.061
8	Sense of humanity at workplace	3.452	3.641	1.1582	.9758	-2.200	.029
9	Linking of work and social goodness of community	3.619	3.237	.8829	1.2743	4.003	.000
10	Promotion of creativeness of spirit of community	3.630	3.396	.9697	1.1285	2.550	.011
11	Staff of my institution support each other	3.678	2.967	1.0184	1.1418	7.920	.000
12	Work spirituality reduces job pressure	3.515	3.404	1.0373	1.0472	1.230	.220
13	Teachers work in the institution as a family	3.522	3.430	.8652	.9758	1.256	.210
14	Increase energy value and spirit of the teachers at the workplace	3.319	3.333	1.0030	1.2164	-.168	.867
15	Connectedness with goals and objectives of the institution	3.515	3.544	1.0480	1.0717	-.355	.723
16	Teachers go to institution happily	3.330	3.378	.9556	1.2094	-.563	.574
17	Teachers feel sense of joy	3.396	3.322	1.0394	1.1225	.820	.413

N=270, $\alpha < .05$

Table 1 indicated that a statistically significant difference was found between two groups of public and private for the first eleven dimensions of workplace spirituality. The value of t-statistics for the first eleven dimensions are significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.485$ & 3.696) for the first dimension of workplace spirituality indicates that the meaningfulness in work better in private schools as compared to the

public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.541$ & 3.393) for the second dimension of workplace spirituality shows that the teachers satisfied with their job seems better in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.563$ & 3.263) for the third dimension of workplace spirituality shows that the work connectedness with life requirement was good in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.844$ & 3.444) for the fourth dimension of workplace spirituality reveals that the teachers think about values and worth of the institution in a better setting in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.419$ & 3.641) for the fifth dimension of workplace spirituality portrays that the teachers promote a climate of mutual trust and respect more in private schools as compared to public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.119$ & 3.519) for the sixth dimension of workplace spirituality reflects that the disciplined is maintained better in private schools as compared to the public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.459$ & 3.615) for the seventh dimension of workplace spirituality shows that priority of caring is important seems good in private schools as compared to the public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.452$ & 3.641) for eight dimension indicates that the sense of humanity at the workplace had given more importance in private schools as compared to public schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.619$ & 3.237) for ninth parameters of workplace spirituality reflects that linking of work and social goodness of community in better experienced in public schools as compared to the private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.630$ & 3.396) for the tenth parameter indicates that the promotion of creativeness of spirit of community more in public schools as compared to private schools. The mean score values ($X^- = 3.678$ & 2.967) for the eleventh dimension of workplace spirituality reflects that the staff of institution support each other in the better way in public schools as compared to the private schools.

The above table 1 also shows that there is no statistically significant difference between two groups of public and private schools for the last six dimensions of workplace spirituality. The value of t-statistics for last six dimensions are not significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The mean score values of dimension of workplace spirituality like work spirituality reduces job pressure, teachers work in the institution as a family and teachers feel sense of joy was found more statistically positive in public schools as compared to private schools while the dimensions like increase energy value and spirit of the teachers at the workplace, connectedness with goals and objectives of the institution and the teachers goes to institution happily experienced well in private schools as compared to public schools.

Discussions and Conclusion

Spirituality advantages workforce and aids organizational outcomes. Spirituality increases workforce well-being, quality of life, a sight of purpose, meaning at work and a sensation of linking and public (Fahri, 2010). Teachers are the main segment of any educational process. The adaptability method is the most formal trait for teaching staff which includes meaningful work and sense of community and the schools enhance compass specific directions which lead to supporting teachers' empowerment via continuous learning (Mousa & Alas, 2016). Pradhan, Jena & Soto (2017) identified the parameters of workplace spirituality which are spiritual connectedness, compassion, meaningful work and alignment of values. Workplace spirituality had a positive relationship with job satisfaction whereas transformational leadership acts as a moderator variable. Higher the spirituality in the workplace will lead to higher the job satisfaction (Nuzulia & Rupiati, 2016). Workplace spirituality affects individuals and organizations through multiple in-depth means (Sheng & Chen, 2012).

The dimensions of workplace spirituality like teachers satisfied with their job, work connectedness with life requirement, teachers think about values and worth of the institution, linking of work and social goodness of community, promotion of creativeness of spirit of community, work spirituality reduces job pressure, teachers work in the institution as a family, and the teachers feel a sense of joy are best experienced in public schools as compared to private schools. The dimensions of workplace spirituality like meaningfulness in work, teachers promotes a climate of mutual trust and respect, disciplined is maintained, priority of caring is important, sense of humanity at the workplace, increase energy value and spirit of the teachers at the workplace, connectedness with goals and objectives of the institution and the teachers goes to institution happily experienced better in private schools as compared to public schools.

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